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Experimental and Numerical Investigation on Lap Shear Fracture of Additively Manufactured Thermoplastic CFRP/64 Titanium

Keiichi Shirasu and Hironori Tohmyoh

Department of Finemechanics, Tohoku University

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTPs)

- A sustainable material that can be reshaped, manufactured at low cost, and has a low environmental impact.

3D printing of CFRTP

- In recent years, the use of composite materials in the manufacture of parts by additive manufacturing (AM) including 3D printing has been attracting attention.
- AM has the advantage of eliminating the need for molds and other tools during fabrication, shortening development lead times, and facilitating the molding of complex shapes that are difficult to fabricate using conventional machining methods.
- The most common 3D printing method: **Fused filament fabrication (FFF)**

CFRTP filament captured with NanoTerasu

Industrial applications

<https://www.electroimpact.com/3d/overview.aspx>

<https://www.arevo.com/?lang=jp>

Robot arm manipulators

Desktop printer

Our group's demonstration

E. Zappino et al., *Composites Part C*, 2 (2020) 100007.

Multi-materialization using CFRP

Expectations for shorter manufacturing processes through reduced mechanical fastening by direct forming (fusion) of dissimilar materials

➤ Previous studies

Aluminum alloy (2024-T3) with alternating layers of PA6 and CF-PA6 (bonding interface is aluminum alloy / PA6)
21.9 MPa shear bond strength^[1]

Alternately forming PA6/66 and CF-PA layers on titanium alloy (Ti-6Al-4V) (Adhesion interface is titanium alloy / PA6/66)

Exploring optimal forming conditions for PA6/66 layers using machine learning^[2]

In both studies, thermoplastic resin filaments were printed on a metal substrate.

➤ This study

Processed metal substrate

3D-printed CFRTP

Heat diffusion

- ✓ Development of a method for directly forming and bonding CFRTP without using resin filaments
- ✓ Examination of fracture mechanisms using finite element analysis

[1] R Falck et al., Materials Letters, **217**(2018), pp211-214.
[2] C Belei et al., Materials & Design, **219**(2022), 110776.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Multimaterial Bonding of Additively Manufactured Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Thermoplastics/64 Titanium

Keiichi Shirasu,* Takeru Mizuno, and Hironori Tohmyoh

The integration of lightweight materials in hybrid structures is critical for achieving energy efficiency in automotive and aerospace industries. This study presents a novel method for directly bonding carbon-fiber-reinforced thermoplastics to Ti6Al4V titanium alloy (64Ti) substrates using fused filament fabrication 3D printing. The technique involves 3D printing short carbon fiber-reinforced polyamide 6 onto sandblasted 64Ti substrates, heated via a hot plate integrated into the 3D printer. Lap-shear tests reveal that adhesion strength improves with increased fusion time, achieving a maximum shear stress of 27.3 ± 2.2 MPa for 60 min welding. Finite element analysis demonstrates stress concentrations at the adhesion edges and highlights the formation of a fracture process zone with localized plastic deformation and microcrack generation. Additionally, the feasibility of fabricating 3D structures and integrating continuous carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastics onto 64Ti substrates is demonstrated. This study advances hybrid material joining techniques by providing a cost-effective, scalable method for achieving robust metal-composite bonds suitable for structural applications.

Experimental procedure: Preparation of 3DP-CFRTP/64Ti hybrids

➤ Materials

Onyx (Markforged, sCFRP/PA6, 10 vol.%)

CFF (Markforged, cCFRTP/PA6, 35 vol.%)

Metal substrate: Sandblasted 64Ti ($R_a=3.3 \mu\text{m}$)

➤ 3D printer

PRUSA MK3S (Prusa Research)

A hot plate (MSA FACTORY) was installed on the build platform of the printer.

➤ Printing conditions

	sCFRTP layer	cCFRTP–first layer	cCFRTP–subsequent layers
Nozzle temperature	230°C	270°C	270°C
Hot plate temperature	180°C	180°C	180°C
Distance between the filaments	0.25 mm	0.5 mm	0.7 mm
Pitch of the layers	0.1 mm	0.125 mm	0.125 mm
Printing speed	300 mm/min	100 mm/min	300 mm/min
Holding time at 270°C after printing	60 min	–	–

Experimental results: Lap-shear tests and fracture surface

Characterization
Lap-shear tests
Shimadzu AGS-X
0.5 mm/min

- ✓ Maximum shear stress = 22.3 ± 0.3 MPa
- ✓ Residual sCFRTP on the 64Ti substrate of the fractured surfaces
→ Strong bonding of the sCFRTP layer to the 64Ti substrate
- ✓ Average thickness of the residual sCFRTP = 19.1 ± 7.1 μ m

Fracture surface (SEM)

Fracture surface (Optical microscope)

LS-DYNA

C3D8 elements

466,432 nodes

433,361 elements

Dimension of the model

Width: 10 mm (sCFRTP/cCFRTP)

12.5 mm (64Ti)

Overlap length: 5 mm

Material/Model(*MAT)	Property	Value
sCFRTP (*MAT_012)	Young's modulus	7.1 GPa ^a
	Poisson's ratio	0.30 ^a
	Yield stress	70 MPa ^a
	Work-hardening rate	450 ^a
64Ti substrate (*MAT_001)	Young's modulus	110 GPa ^b
	Poisson's ratio	0.33
Polyimide film (*MAT_001)	Young's modulus	3.4 GPa
	Poisson's ratio	0.30
CFRTP laminate (*MAT_002)	Longitudinal Young's modulus	61.3 GPa ^c
	Transverse Young's modulus	4.5 GPa ^c
	Longitudinal shear modulus (G_{12})	2.0 GPa ^c
	Transverse shear modulus (G_{13}, G_{23})	2.4, 1.6 GPa ^c
	Longitudinal Poisson's ratio (ν_{12})	0.48 ^c
	Transverse Poisson's ratio (ν_{13}, ν_{23})	0.34, 0.41 ^c

a: Ref [1], b: Ref [2], c: Ref [3]

[1] K. Shirasu et al., Adv. Eng. Mater. 2402221 27 (2025) 2402221.

[2] M. Kheradmandfard et al., Ultrason. Sonochem. 39 (2017) 698–706.

[3] Y. Hoshikawa et al., J. Thermoplast. Compos. Mater. 36 (2023) 2836–2861.

The strain histories obtained from the mesoscale FEA were input to a micromechanics model¹ incorporating Christensen's failure criterion².

¹K. Shirasu, et al., Mater. Sci. Eng. A 891 (2024) 145971.

²R.M. Christensen, J. Appl. Mech. 87 (2020) 051001.

Stress increment of the sCFRTP

$$\Delta\sigma_{UD}^{ply} = D_{UD}^{ply} R(\theta) \Delta\hat{\epsilon}_c^{FEM}$$

$$= D_{UD}^{ply} R(\theta) (\Delta\hat{\epsilon}_x \quad \Delta\hat{\epsilon}_y \quad \Delta\hat{\epsilon}_z \quad \Delta\hat{\gamma}_{yz} \quad \Delta\hat{\gamma}_{zx} \quad \Delta\hat{\gamma}_{xy})^T$$

D_{UD}^{ply} is derived by EMT model

Stress increment in the matrix

$$\Delta\sigma_m^{ply} = D_m(S - I) \{ (1 - V_f) [(D_f - D_m)S + D_m] + V_f D_f \}^{-1}$$

$$\times [(D_f - D_m)S + D_m] (S - I)^{-1} D_m^{-1} \Delta\sigma_{UD}^{ply}$$

$$\sigma_m^{ply} = (\sigma_x \quad \sigma_y \quad \sigma_z \quad \tau_{yz} \quad \tau_{zx} \quad \tau_{xy})^T$$

Christensen failure criterion

$$F_{chris} = \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{C} \right) (\sigma_x + \sigma_y + \sigma_z)$$

$$+ \frac{3}{2TC} \{ \sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_z^2 + 2(\tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2 + \tau_{xy}^2) \}$$

- The Christensen failure function F_{Chris} exceeded 1 when the macroscopic shear stress reached approximately 17 MPa, indicating the onset of resin damage (Region (i)).
- The area under $F_{Chris} > 1$ expanded progressively with increasing macroscopic stress (Regions (ii) and (iii)).
- When the macroscopic stress reached the failure stress (22.3 MPa), the region satisfying $F_{Chris} > 1$ developed into a quarter-elliptical shape centered around the precrack tip (Region (iv)), extending up to 27 and 22 μm in the bonded interface and thickness directions, respectively.

This study developed a multimaterial additive manufacturing technique for fabricating hybrid joints composed of continuous carbon fiber-reinforced PA6 (cCFRTP) and 64Ti substrates.

Experiments

Lap-shear specimens fabricated through this method exhibited a maximum shear stress of 22.3 ± 0.3 MPa, confirming strong interfacial adhesion without adhesives or surface primers. Fractographic observations revealed cohesive failure within the sCFRTP, suggesting an anchoring effect induced by thermal softening.

FEA

The FEA demonstrated that the FPZ, where the Christensen failure index $F_{\text{Chris}} > 1$, was observed to extend over a 27 μm wide region along the interface and to distribute through a thickness of approximately 21 μm between the polyimide film and the titanium substrate. The numerical visualization of the FPZ provides valuable insights into the interfacial fracture mechanism.

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Micromechanics model with Christensen's failure criterion

→ Treat composite materials with fiber orientation distribution as a model of overlapping unidirectional materials with different fiber principal axes orientation.

1. Effective tensile modulus: Eshelby model combined with the Mori–Tanaka theory

Elastic modulus \mathbf{D}_{UD} for each ply in the local coordinate system (fiber orientation direction)

$$\mathbf{D}_{UD} = \mathbf{D}_m \{ (1 - V_f)(\mathbf{D}_f - \mathbf{D}_m)\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{D}_m \}^{-1} [(1 - V_f)\{(\mathbf{D}_f - \mathbf{D}_m)\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{D}_m\} + V_f\mathbf{D}_f]$$

\mathbf{D}_m : Stiffness matrix of resin, V_f : Fiber volume fraction, \mathbf{S} : Eshelby tensor

2. Elastic modulus of each ply in the overall coordinate system (tensile direction)

$$\tilde{\mathbf{D}}_{UD} = \mathbf{T}^{-1} \mathbf{D}_{UD} \mathbf{R}$$

3. Elastic modulus of composite in the overall coordinate system (averaged according to orientation distribution)

$$\tilde{\mathbf{D}}_c = \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} f(\theta) \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_{UD} d\theta$$

4. Incremental strain in composite → Obtain stress-strain diagram

$$\Delta \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_c = \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_c^{-1} \Delta \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_c$$

5. Stress increments for each ply in the local coordinate system

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{UD} = \mathbf{D}_{UD} \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_c = \mathbf{D}_{UD} \mathbf{R} \Delta \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_c$$

6. Incremental stress on the fibers of each ply in the local coordinate system

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_f = \mathbf{D}_m (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) \{ (1 - V_f) [(\mathbf{D}_f - \mathbf{D}_m) \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{D}_m] + V_f \mathbf{D}_f \}^{-1} \mathbf{D}_f (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I})^{-1} \mathbf{D}_m^{-1} \Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{UD}$$

7. Incremental stress on the resin of each ply in the local coordinate system

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_m = \mathbf{D}_m (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) \{ (1 - V_f) [(\mathbf{D}_f - \mathbf{D}_m) \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{D}_m] + V_f \mathbf{D}_f \}^{-1} \{ (\mathbf{D}_f - \mathbf{D}_m) \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{D}_m \} (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I})^{-1} \mathbf{D}_m^{-1} \Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{UD}$$

Eshelby tensor, \mathbf{S} , for continuous fiber

8. Equivalent Young's modulus and equivalent Poisson's ratio after yielding

$$E' = \frac{E_m}{1 + E_m/H'} \quad \nu' = \frac{\nu_m + E_m/2H'}{1 + E_m/H'}$$

Judgment of yield point (switch to plastic deformation)

If Mises stress (equivalent stress) $\sigma_e \geq \sigma_r$, switch to elastoplasticity.

$$\sigma_e = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \sigma'_{ij} \sigma'_{ij}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left\{ (\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 + (\sigma_y - \sigma_z)^2 + (\sigma_z - \sigma_x)^2 + 6(\tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2 + \tau_{xy}^2) \right\}^{1/2}}$$

Work hardening coefficient (ratio of equivalent incremental stress to equivalent incremental plastic strain)

$$H' = \frac{d\sigma_e}{d\varepsilon_e^p} \quad \sigma_e = c(a + \varepsilon_e^p)^N \quad \text{Swift's equation}$$

9. Christensen's failure criterion

Calculated using the stress σ_m of the resin in the local coordinate system.

Failure is determined when the left-hand side exceeds 1.

$$\left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{C}\right) \sigma_{ii} + \frac{3}{2TC} \sigma'_{ij} \sigma'_{ij}$$

T : Tensile strength
C : Compressive strength

$$= \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{C}\right) (\sigma_x + \sigma_y + \sigma_z) + \frac{3}{2TC} \left\{ \sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_z^2 + 2(\tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2 + \tau_{xy}^2) \right\} \leq 1$$